

Synthesis and Structure of Dipropionylacetone and of Di-*n*-butyrylacetone.

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Collie's structure of diacetylacetone (I) as against the open-chain ketonic or enolic structure, is based upon facts such as : -

(a) Absence of ketonic reactions in the compound. (Collie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **85**, 971).

(b) Inequivalence of the two replaceable hydrogen atoms in it. (Collie and Reilly, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **119**, 1550).

This structure is also supported by the value of its molecular refraction determined by Homfray (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **87**, 1451), which does not agree with the open-chain structure.

To throw more light on the structure of diacetylacetone it was thought desirable to synthesise and study the higher homologues namely dipropionylacetone and di-*n*-butyrylacetone from diethylpyrone and di-*n*-propylpyrone respectively, synthesised by one of us (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **9**, 303). These compounds to which the structures (II) and (III) respectively may provisionally be given were obtained from the corresponding pyrones as in the preparation of diacetylacetone.

The compound (II), when freshly distilled, is a yellow liquid which slowly changes into red one, this change being accompanied by change in refractive index and structure. The change is much slower than in the case of diacetylacetone. The yellow and red forms may be called the α - and β - form respectively. The β - form changes back into the α - form on distillation. The two forms give different sets of reactions.

The compound (III) is a brownish yellow liquid and when pure does not seem to undergo a change in its refractive index.

By the action of phenylhydrazine on dimethylpyrone carboxylic acid Feist and Bellart (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1817) obtained a yellow solid having the composition $C_{19}H_{22}ON_4$ and a white solid $C_{19}H_{20}N_4$. They considered the yellow solid to be the diphenylhydrazone of diacetylacetone. This was later prepared by Collie from diacetylacetone itself (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1984) but was found to have the composition $C_{19}H_{20}N_4$ which cannot be that of a diphenylhydrazone. Collie did not investigate the structure of this compound.

Dipropionylacetone and di-*n*-butyrylacetone were treated with phenylhydrazine, but the reaction products were viscous liquids from which no definite compounds could be isolated.

The use of *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine in place of phenylhydrazine gave unexpected results. One molecule of the α -form of dipropionylacetone reacts with 1 molecule of nitrophenylhydrazine with elimination of 2 molecules of water and formation of a compound $C_{15}H_{17}N_3O_3$ melting at 78° . The β - form fails to produce this compound. One molecule of it, however, reacts with 2 molecules of nitrophenylhydrazine and gives with elimination of 3 molecules of water a compound, $C_{21}H_{22}O_4N_6$ melting at 164° .

By the action of the barium salt of dipropionylacetone (1 mol.) and nitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride (2 mols.) a third compound was obtained (m.p. 141°) having the composition $C_{21}H_{24}O_5N_6$ which is that of a dinitrophenylhydrazone.

None of the compounds melting at 78° and 164° can be a true phenylhydrazone as in their formation the number of water molecules eliminated exceeds the number of nitrophenylhydrazine molecules reacted by one. This additional molecule of water must obviously come from the ketone, a process which will result in ring-formation. (IV) or (V) are, therefore, the possible structures of the compound melting at 78° .

(IV)

(V)

(IV) is nitrophenylhydrazone of diethylpyrone, a compound which has not so far been obtained from diethylpyrone itself (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 303). (V) is *N*-nitrophenyliminodiethylpyridone. The possible structure of the compound melting at 164° is (VI) which is that of the nitrophenylhydrazone of (V).

(VI)

The structures are finally confirmed as follows. The compound melting at 164° behaves like a pyridone. It is a mono-acid base and forms a hydrochloride and a chloroplatinate. It also behaves like a phenylhydrazone. On hydrolysis it gives the compound melting at 78°. Both these reactions are in agreement with the structure (VI). As regards the compound melting at 78° the following facts prove that its structure is (V) and not (IV). It is a mono-acid base and forms a chloroplatinate. It is obtained by hydrolysis of (VI) containing two $>\text{N—NH—C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NO}_2$ groups of which one forming part of the ring cannot be removed during hydrolysis. It is not further hydrolysable to diethylpyrone. The compound (VI) could not, however, be synthesised from (V) and nitrophenylhydrazine.

The dinitrophenylhydrazone melting at 148° is not basic. Its structure can be either (VII) or (VIII).

In di-*n*-butyrylacetone the middle carbonyl group yields to phenylhydrazone formation (*vide infra*). If, therefore, one can go by analogy, for the compound melting at 148° the structure (VIII) is preferred to (VII).

Freshly prepared di-*n*-butyrylacetone reacts with one molecule of nitrophenylhydrazine and gives a yellow compound melting at 71° and having the composition $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_4\text{N}_3$ which is that of a mono-nitrophenylhydrazone. The presence of di-*n*-butyrylacetone among the products of hydrolysis of the compound melting at 71° could be demonstrated, which proves that the compound is a true phenylhydrazone. In contact with strong hydrochloric acid and platinic chloride this compound gives a chloroplatinate whose composition is that of the chloroplatinate of nitrophenylhydrazone of di-*n*-propylpyrone (X). It is, therefore, obvious that in the compound melting at 71° the middle carbonyl group of the triketone has yielded to phenylhydrazone formation and, therefore, its structure is (IX).

The action of two molecules of nitrophenylhydrazine on di-*n*-butyrylacetone gives the corresponding pyridone phenylhydrazone (XI) which resembles its lower homologue in all its chemical reactions.

(XI)

These reactions of these two triketones can be readily explained by their open-chain ketonic or enolic formulæ.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Dipropionylacetone (II).—To the aqueous solution of pure diethylpyrone was added a hot concentrated solution of barium hydroxide in excess and the mixture heated to boiling for 5 minutes, when the barium salt of dipropionylacetone precipitated as a pale yellow solid. This was filtered, washed and decomposed by cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The ketone separated as an oil which was extracted with chloroform. On drying and removal of the solvent the residual liquid was distilled at 117°/6 mm. (Found: C, 63·7; H, 8·0. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 63·5 ; H, 8·2 per cent).

Freshly distilled dipropionylacetone (α -form) is a yellow liquid with a strong pleasant odour. $d_4^{20} = 1\cdot032$; $n_D^{20} = 1\cdot4999$.

The molecular refraction $\frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{M}{\alpha} = 48\cdot4$

The value calculated for $\text{Et}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{Et} = 44\cdot04$

$\text{Et}\cdot\text{C}(\text{OH}) = \text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH} = \text{C}(\text{OH})\cdot\text{Et}$
 $= 45\cdot92$

$\text{Et}\cdot\text{C}(\text{OH}) = \text{CH}\cdot\text{C}(\text{OH}) = \text{CH}\cdot\text{C}(\text{OH}) =$
 $\text{CH}\cdot\text{Me} = 48\cdot92$

The value calculated for

= 47.99 * (using 2.65 as the value of atomic refraction of quadrivalent oxygen indirectly obtained by Homfray, *loc. cit.*).

After standing for 3 days the colour of the compound changed to red and refractive index rose to 1.5044 which then remained constant. The ketone gives violet colour with ferric chloride and forms a sparingly soluble copper salt. When its solution in aqueous methyl alcohol containing a trace of hydrochloric acid is boiled for one hour it is converted into diethylpyrone.

The pyridone (V).—The best yield of this compound was obtained when the ketone (1 mol.) and nitrophenylhydrazine (0.8 mol.) were heated together in absolute alcoholic solution on a water-bath for 20 minutes. On concentrating and leaving overnight the mass became semi-solid which was spread on a porous tile. The solid obtained was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in almost colourless needles m. p. 78°. (Found: C, 62.4; H, 5.6; N, 15.1. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires C, 62.7; H, 5.9; N, 14.7 per cent).

The chloroplatinate of the pyridone was prepared by adding platinum chloride to the solution of the pyridone in strong hydrochloric acid. It is an orange solid melting at 198° [Found: Pt, 20.5. $(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3)_2\text{H}_2\text{PtCl}_6$ requires Pt, 19.8 per cent].

The phenylhydrazone (VI).—The ketone (β -form, 1 mol.) and nitrophenylhydrazine (2 mols.) were heated in absolute alcoholic solution for 20 minutes. On removing the solvent the sticky mass was rubbed with glacial acetic acid, when a yellow solid separated. This was crystallised from pyridine in needles, m. p. 164°. (Found: C, 59.1; H, 5.0; N, 19.8. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6$ requires C, 59.7; H, 5.2; N, 19.9 per cent).

* The value 47.99 is given for molecular refraction of dipropionylacetone using a simple ring-formula.

The chloroplatinate of (VI) was prepared as that of (V). It is a yellow solid melting at 157°. [Found: Pt, 15.5. $(C_{21}H_{22}O_4N_6)_2 \cdot H_2PtCl_6$ requires Pt, 15.5 per cent].

Hydrolysis of (VI).—The compound was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and was refluxed for 1 hour in a current of dry hydrochloric acid. On cooling the product was poured into water and the turbid mass filtered. The filtrate deposited on standing a small amount of crystalline compound in the form of needles. This on drying melted at 78° and was identified as the pyridone (V) by mixed melting point.

The dinitrophenylhydrazone (VIII).—Barium salt of the ketone (1 mol.) and nitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride (2 mols.) were well shaken in absolute ether for one day. The ethereal layer was decanted off and the remaining solid was washed repeatedly with dilute acetic acid to dissolve barium chloride and the unchanged substances. The dinitrophenylhydrazone is a brownish yellow solid and was crystallised twice from pyridine in small needles melting at 148°. (Found: N, 19.68. $C_{21}H_{24}O_5N_6$ requires N, 19.1 per cent). The substance was insufficient for estimations of C and H.

Di-n-butyrylacetone (III) was prepared in the same way as its lower homologue. Its barium salt is less readily formed and in smaller yield. The salt is decomposed by exposure to air. The ketone is a liquid showing great tendency to pass into dipropylpyrone, for when it was distilled under reduced pressure the distillate contained the pyrone which was identified in the form of its chloroplatinate. When, however, a small amount of the liquid was quickly distilled it boiled at 136°/4 mm. It is a brownish yellow liquid with a strong pleasant odour resembling that of its lower homologue, $n_D^{20} = 1.4856$. It colours ferric chloride violet. (Found: C, 65.9; H, 8.6. $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 66.7; H, 9.1 per cent).

The copper salt was obtained by shaking the ketone with aqueous copper acetate. It is a bluish green solid insoluble in water and alcohol. (Found: Cu, 24.0. $C_{11}H_{18}O_3Cu$ requires Cu, 24.6 per cent).

The phenylhydrazone (IX).—For the preparation of this compound fresh and fairly pure form of the ketone was required which was obtained from the above copper salt by decomposing it with an acid. When the ketone and nitrophenylhydrazine in equimolecular proportions were heated together in absolute alcohol for 20 minutes and the solvent evaporated the phenylhydrazone was obtained from the residue on rubbing. It was crystallised from alcohol or petroleum ether in

pale yellow needles melting at 71° . (Found: C, 61.4; H, 6.8; N, 13.1. $C_{17}H_{23}O_4N_3$ requires C, 61.3; H, 6.9; N, 12.6 per cent).

When the compound (IX) was left in contact with strong hydrochloric acid and platinum chloride overnight, the *chloroplatinate* of (X) was slowly formed. [Found: Pt, 18.8. $(C_{17}H_{21}O_3N_3)_2H_2PtCl_6$ requires Pt, 18.8 per cent].

The phenylhydrazone (IX) was hydrolysed by dry hydrochloric acid in boiling acetic acid solution. On pouring the solution into water a mass of the unchanged phenylhydrazone precipitated and was removed by filtration. On neutralising the filtrate and boiling with barium hydroxide a small quantity of the barium salt of the ketone (III) separated as a solid. When the barium salt was acidified the ketone was formed and was recognised by its odour and its ferric chloride reaction.

The phenylhydrazone (XI).—It was prepared from the ketone which had stood for some days. Its preparation is similar to that of the compound (VI). It was crystallised from alcohol in deep yellow needles melting at 140° . (Found: C, 61.3; H, 5.2; N, 18.7. $C_{23}H_{26}O_4N_6$ requires C, 61.3; H, 5.7; N, 18.7 per cent).